

Composition, Stability, and Analytical Applications of Scandium-1-(*o*-arsonophenylazo)-2-naphthol-3,6-disulphonate Chelate*

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The composition of scandium-1-(*o*-arsonophenylazo)-2-naphthol-3,6-disulphonate (Thoron) chelate ($\lambda_{\max}$ 500 m μ) has been inferred to be 1:2, using absorptiometric measurements by three different methods. The chelate is stable between pH 3.5 and 7.5. The stability constant, as determined by different methods, is of the order of 10^9 at pH 4.0 and at 25°. The system has been found to adhere to Beer's law between 0.12 p.p.m. and 3.2 p.p.m. of scandium over a wide range of temperature and between pH 3.5 and 7.5. The sensitivity (Sandell) is 0.022 γ/cm^2 . Interference by a number of ions has been noted and their tolerance limit determined.

The composition, stability, and analytical applications of chelates of 1-(*o*-arsonophenylazo)-2-naphthol-3,6-disulphonate (Thoron) with thorium, uranium, palladium, and lanthanum have already been reported¹⁻³. The formation of red-coloured chelates with scandium, yttrium, and rare earths has also been noted. This communication records results on the scandium-Thoron chelate.

EXPERIMENTAL

Aqueous solutions of scandium chloride (Johnson Matthey & Co.) and 1-(*o*-arsonophenylazo)-2-naphthol-3,6-disulphonate (sodium salt, B.D.H.) were prepared.

Absorbance measurements were made with a Unicam SP 500 spectrophotometer, operated by Doran's mains unit connected to 200 V/50 cycles a.c. mains, using 10 mm matched glass cells.

pH measurements were done with a Leeds and Northrup direct-reading pH indicator, using glass calomel electrodes.

DISCUSSION

Nature of the Complexes formed.—Employing the method of Vosburgh and Cooper⁴, only one chelate having $\lambda_{\max}$ at 500 m μ (Fig. 1) was found to form.

Composition of the Chelate.—Three different methods, viz., Job's method of continued variations⁴, mole-ratio method⁵, and slope-ratio method⁶, were employed

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3. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 437.

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to establish the composition of the chelate. The composition of the chelate has been found to be 1:2 by all the methods (Fig. 2, 3 & 4). Hence the formula of the chelate may be designated as $\text{Sc}(\text{Thoron})_2$.

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of scandium-Thoron chelate.

Curve A. Thoron: $8.0 \times 10^{-5} M$.

Curve B. Thoron: $8.0 \times 10^{-5} M$; ScCl_3 : $4.0 \times 10^{-5} M$.

Curve C. Thoron: $8.0 \times 10^{-5} M$; ScCl_3 : $2.0 \times 10^{-5} M$.

Effect of pH on the Stability of the Chelate.—A mixture containing $4.0 \times 10^{-4} M$ Thoron and $2.0 \times 10^{-4} M$ scandium chloride retained the value of its λ_{max} (500 μ) between pH 3.5 and 7.5.

Evaluation of the Stability Constant.—Stability constant ($\log K$) of the chelate, determined by the application of the method of Dey *et al.*⁷, mole-ratio method⁸, and by Job's method⁴, using nonequimolecular solutions of pH 4.0 and at 545 μ , are respectively, 8.4 ± 0.4 , 8.6 ± 0.4 , and 8.9 ± 0.2 .

Adherence to Beer's Law.—To 10 ml of the reagent solution varying volumes (1, 2, 3 . . . 9 ml) of scandium chloride were added and the volumes raised to 25 ml in each case. The colour intensity was measured with a Unicam SP 500 spectrophotometer at 545 μ . The system was found to obey Beer's law over the range of 0.12 to 3.2 p.p.m. of scandium.

FIG. 2. Job's method.
($p=1$)

Curve A: $4.0 \times 10^{-4} M$.

Curve B: $2.0 \times 10^{-4} M$.

Curve C: $1.33 \times 10^{-4} M$.

FIG. 3

Mole-ratio method at 545 μ ,

pH 4.0. Final conc. of Thoron:

Curve A: $1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$.

Curve B: $0.87 \times 10^{-5} M$.

